

Containerization of Real-time Streaming of Scientific Data in HPC: Challenges and Solutions

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Abstract—In this paper, we will explore the containerization focusing on scientific simulation data such as NWChem and the Open Catalyst OCP. Additionally, how singularity containers are used to containerize HPC applications. We run different machine learning frameworks with and without Singularity containers show their performance and challenges of integrating containerization technologies within High-Performance Computing (HPC) environments, particularly for applications in computational chemistry and materials science. We also highlighted the limitations of traditional containerization tools such as Docker in supercomputing contexts and introduced Singularity as a more suitable alternative tailored to HPC requirements. By analyzing the containerization process of NWChem and OCP project at the NERSC PERLMUTTER supercomputer at LBNL, we illustrate how Singularity effectively addresses HPC-specific needs while ensuring performance and scalability. Our findings offer valuable insights for optimizing containerization strategies for complex scientific software in advanced computing environments.

Index Terms—Containers, Singularity, HPC, NWChem and OCP

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of containerization in computing has revolutionized software deployment and management, particularly in computational chemistry and materials science. This technology provides a lightweight, portable, and consistent environment for complex applications like NWChem, a widely utilized computational chemistry software package. By allowing researchers to package NWChem with all its dependencies, containerization ensures reproducibility and simplifies deployment across diverse computing environments. Though containerization has become popular in cloud and enterprise computing, it presents the huge challenge while implementing projects like Open Catalyst Dataset analysis in High-Performance Computing (HPC) environments. Due to HPC systems large-scale data processing from intensive simulations, which demands bare-metal performance, requires specialized hardware such as GPU, and security concerns. These requirements are frequently at odds with conventional containerization approaches. The computational demands of NWChem simulations and the processing of vast datasets like the Open Catalyst project, which aims to discover new catalysts for renewable energy applications, exemplify the need for specialized containerization solutions in HPC environments. These solutions must provide the benefits of containers—such as portability and consistent environments—while addressing the specific requirements of supercomputing platforms used in advanced chemical and

materials research. Recognizing these distinct needs, the HPC community, including researchers working with NWChem and Open Catalyst data, has sought tailored containerization solutions. These specialized approaches aim to leverage the advantages of containerization while maintaining the high performance and security standards essential for cutting-edge computational chemistry and materials science research in supercomputing environments.

II. MOTIVATION

The motivation for comparing Singularity and Docker in the context of real-time streaming of scientific data in HPC environments arises from the distinctive challenges inherent in modern scientific computing workflows [1]. As the volume and speed of scientific data—especially in fields like computational chemistry and initiatives such as the Open Catalyst Project (OCP)—expand exponentially, the need for efficient, secure, and high-performance containerization solutions becomes more critical. While Docker is a powerful tool in enterprise settings, it encounters several limitations in HPC environments, including security vulnerabilities, resource management conflicts, and performance overheads. These issues become particularly pronounced in scenarios involving real-time streaming of large-scale scientific data, where even minor delays or inefficiencies can significantly affect the quality and timeliness of research. Singularity, designed with HPC environments in mind, offers potential solutions to these challenges by improving processing efficiency, enhancing security for sensitive data, and integrating more seamlessly with existing HPC infrastructure. By evaluating Singularity and Docker for real-time data streaming, we aim to find the most effective strategies for handling the complex, data-intensive workflows typical of modern scientific computing. This comparison will ultimately support more rapid and robust scientific discoveries in fields dependent on HPC resources.

Docker: Limitations for NWChem in HPC Environments:

- **Security Risks:** Docker’s need for root privileges poses significant security risks in shared HPC facilities. Granting such access can compromise system integrity and create administrative challenges, particularly in multi-user environments where principles of least privilege are essential [2].
- **Resource Management Incompatibility:** Docker does not natively integrate with HPC schedulers like Slurm or

PBS, leading to potential inefficiencies in resource allocation for NWChem simulations. This mismatch can impact the performance and scheduling of large-scale quantum chemistry calculations.

- **Networking Issues:** Docker’s complex networking model, including NAT and virtual networks, can conflict with the low-latency, high-bandwidth requirements of distributed NWChem applications. This can introduce latency and reduce bandwidth, affecting the performance of extensive simulations.
- **Performance Overhead:** The layered architecture of Docker can introduce performance overheads that are significant for NWChem’s computationally intensive workloads. Even small inefficiencies can impact the performance of large-scale, critical quantum chemistry simulations.

Singularity: Adapted Containerization for NWChem and OCP [3]

- **Enhanced Security:** Singularity’s user-space implementation avoids the need for root privileges, aligning with HPC security policies and preventing privilege escalation. This is crucial for protecting sensitive data in projects like OCP.
- **Resource Management Compatibility:** Singularity integrates seamlessly with HPC job management systems, allowing efficient resource allocation for NWChem jobs. This compatibility supports complex simulations without disrupting established HPC workflows.
- **Near-Native Performance:** Singularity offers near-native performance by providing direct access to high-performance hardware and interconnects. This reduces virtualization overhead, essential for computationally intensive quantum chemistry calculations.
- **Efficient Data Sharing:** Singularity enables native access to host file systems, facilitating efficient data sharing between the container and the host. This is crucial for managing and processing large datasets in OCP research.
- **MPI Support:** Singularity’s robust support for MPI is critical for parallel NWChem computations, enabling complex simulations across multiple nodes [4]. This is vital for extensive computational tasks, such as those required for OCP research. By addressing these key aspects, Singularity provides a containerization solution specifically tailored to the needs of NWChem and projects like OCP in HPC environments, balancing the benefits of containerization with the unique requirements of high-performance computational chemistry research.

III. PROPOSED RESEARCH AND ITS CHALLENGES

The proposed research introduces a pioneering approach to real-time containerization of scientific data, demonstrated by simulations from NWChem and OCP. Utilizing ADIOS with MPI4py for communication between a producer and multiple consumers [5] as shown in Fig. 1, this approach aims to integrate effectively with existing frameworks, offering a more targeted and efficient data reduction strategy that

preserves essential scientific insights. Despite its potential, the research faces challenges such as time constraints, limited testing restricted to a single dataset (the Collision dataset), and potential scalability issues. To address these, future work will focus on expanding the range of test cases, conducting comprehensive performance analyses, developing adaptive criteria selection methods, and implementing robust validation techniques. These efforts are crucial for validating the approach’s effectiveness across diverse scientific scenarios. Overall, the producer and multiple consumer model shows considerable promise for enhancing data management in scientific simulations, potentially optimizing computational resource use while maintaining the integrity of critical scientific information.

Fig. 1: Sample Docker Built for Molecular Dynamics Data

IV. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the proposed real-time containerization approach represents a significant advancement in managing scientific data from simulations like NWChem and OCP. By dynamically selecting and storing key data points, it offers a more efficient and targeted data reduction strategy compared to traditional offline methods. While challenges such as time constraints, limited initial testing, and scalability issues remain, the potential benefits—improved data management, optimized resource use, and preservation of critical insights—underscore the approach’s promise. Future research and validation will be essential to fully realize its effectiveness and applicability across diverse scientific scenarios.

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